

The Perception of Parents and Students on the Implementation of the Mandatory Basic ROTC Program in the Philippines

Thomas Andrei C. Brecio, Geo Albert B. Bravo, Ma Hannah Delina, Franchesca Nicole V. De Vera
Senior High School Department
Nazareth School of National University Manila, Philippines

Abstract:- This study aimed to investigate the perception of students and parents regarding the implementation of the Mandatory Basic Reserve Officers' Training Corps (MBROTC) Program. Specifically, the study focused on students' social development, disaster preparedness and national security, and issues related to the program. A descriptive research design was employed. Using quota sampling, participants were 196 senior high school students and 196 parents in Metro Manila, Philippines. A researcher-made questionnaire was distributed online and face-to-face which went through the process of content validity and reliability. The findings revealed that both students and parents agreed that the MBROTC Program would effectively contribute to social development, disaster preparedness and national security. However, they expressed uncertainty regarding its effectiveness in instilling patriotism and potential risks to overall well-being. Additionally, parents agreed that the program would enhance the country's ability to respond to natural disasters and internal and external threats but were unsure about its impact on a student's mental well-being. Future research can explore the reasons behind the uncertainty found in the results. Understanding these reasons will inform policymakers in refining the program, addressing concerns, and fostering greater acceptance and support among students and parents, ultimately ensuring the program's successful implementation and achievement of its goals.

Keywords:- Mandatory ROTC; Social Development; Disaster Preparedness and National Securities; Issues, Philippines

I. INTRODUCTION

The Reserve Officers' Training Corps (ROTC) program was initially established in the Philippines through the 1935 National Defense Act under the administration of Manuel L. Quezon, as mandated by Executive Order No. 207, to develop the youth's ability to defend the nation against external threats (Yabes & Nazareno, 2001). As part of the National Service Training Program (NSTP), the ROTC program plays a crucial role in providing military training to citizen soldiers, organizing, and mobilizing them for national defense preparedness (Department of Military Science and Tactics, 2020). According to the Republic Act No. 9163, the NSTP comprises three program components: ROTC, Literacy Training Service, and Civic Welfare Training Service, all designed to foster civic consciousness, promote defense preparedness, and instill the values of

service and patriotism among the youth. The NSTP curriculum emphasizes the importance of being a responsible Filipino with social sensitivity toward societal issues (Atillano et al., 2022). The goal of the ROTC program is to equip high school students with leadership skills while imparting knowledge about their rights, duties, and privileges (Quezada, 2020). Furthermore, the ROTC program is regarded as a means to cultivate discipline, accountability, and character-building, while enhancing students' leadership capabilities (Philippine Information Agency, 2022).

According to the proposed bill, the Mandatory Basic ROTC (MBROTC) program encompasses training in external and territorial defense, internal security and public safety, disaster risk management, and humanitarian rights. Advocates argue that implementing the MBROTC Program will contribute to the country's overall security. While existing studies have explored the perception and effects of the ROTC and NSTP programs, they have predominantly focused on college students who voluntarily enrolled in the program. Notably, there is a lack of research examining the perception of parents regarding the ROTC Program in the Philippines, highlighting a significant knowledge gap. Thus, this study aims to address this gap by investigating the perception of both parents and students regarding the implementation of the MBROTC Program in the Philippines.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter explored various aspects of the ROTC Program, providing valuable insights into its contextualization, implementation, and effects. It encompasses a wide range of topics, including the historical background of the ROTC Program in the Philippines, issues within the current ROTC Program, perceptions of students and parents, and the effects of the program on students.

A. *The ROTC Program in the Philippines*

The Reserve Officers' Training Corps (ROTC) program was first introduced in the Philippines through the 1935 National Defense Act, implemented by Manuel L. Quezon under Executive Order No. 207. Its integration into an undergraduate student's curriculum was later established under sections 38 and 39 of Republic Act 7077, aiming to mobilize students for national defense and preparedness. However, Republic Act No. 9163 of 2002 made ROTC an optional program alongside two other subprograms under the National Service Training Program (NSTP).

During the 2022 State of the Nation Address, President Marcos urged Congress to enact a law mandating the inclusion of the ROTC program among Senior High School students. In response, several senators submitted bills proposing the mandatory implementation of the ROTC program for undergraduate students (S.B No. 236, 2022; S.B No. 1551, 2022). Notably, Senate Bill No. 236 was presented to the Senate of the Philippines in 2022, aiming to establish the Mandatory Basic Reserve Officers' Training Corps (MBROTC) program and restore the ROTC program in general.

The MBROTC program will consist of various military training components, including external and territorial defense, security and public safety, disaster mitigation, and humanitarian laws. Undergraduate students will be required to complete the program for two years, and failure to do so will disqualify them from graduating with their degrees. Senate Bill No. 1551, introduced in 2022, proposed the "Mandatory Basic Reserve Officers Training Corps (ROTC) Act," which seeks to enforce the ROTC program. The program will encompass modules that enhance students' willingness to serve the public, foster respect for human rights, cultivate an appreciation for national heroes, and develop self-discipline and critical thinking. Additionally, it will incorporate military training to inspire students' dedication to serving their country and ensuring its security.

B. Issues With the Current ROTC Program

In 2001, an ROTC student at a university in the Philippines filed a complaint against the Department of Military Science and Tactics for alleged bribery and corruption. Tragically, four months later, the student's body was discovered wrapped in a carpet floating in the Pasig River. In response to this incident, R.A. No. 9163 was enacted to address the corruption within the ROTC program, following student protests calling for the abolition of the MBROTC Program. Additionally, the Anti-Hazing Act was implemented to specifically tackle hazing issues within the ROTC program, aiming to prohibit and penalize any cadet supervisor who engages in or puts student cadets at risk of hazing.

C. Perception of Students on the ROTC Program

A study conducted by Tullao (2019) examined the perceptions of 324 Criminology students at Bulacan State University regarding the ROTC program. The study utilized questionnaires to evaluate aspects such as management, instructions, and training facilities. The results indicated a high level of satisfaction with the program, highlighting the significance of effective management, quality instructions, well-equipped classrooms, and training materials for successful implementation in tertiary institutions. Furthermore, Ortaez (2023) explored the Philippine educational crisis from the perspectives of three educators at different levels: primary, secondary, and tertiary. The study identified conflicting priorities hindering the establishment of an educational standard and proposed measures such as revising the current K-12 curriculum, developing comprehensive plans, and improving learning materials to address the crisis effectively. It is important to note that

solely implementing a mandatory ROTC program will not resolve this issue.

D. Perception of Parents on the ROTC Program

Lindsey (2022) conducted a study on parents' perceptions of the Junior Reserve Training Corps (JROTC) program in the Northeast region of the US, employing Vroom's motivational theory and Maslow's needs hierarchy. The findings indicated that parents considered the JROTC program to be valuable and beneficial for their children's high school experience. Another study by Quezada (2020) focused on the Marine Corps Junior Reserve Officers' Training Corps program, aiming to increase participation by dispelling misconceptions among non-participating students and parents. The study employed transformative and authentic leadership, Critical Race Theory, and Maslow's hierarchical needs paradigm. The research highlighted the prevalence of misconceptions among parents and non-participating students, significantly impacting program participation. Furthermore, it confirmed existing research on the positive effects of the program on participating students, recommending the implementation of an assertive communication strategy to convey the program's official purpose and its impact.

E. The Effect of the ROTC Program on Students

A study conducted by Pacatang and Montallana (2022) examined the impact of the NSTP ROTC program on student cadets' behavioral formation. The study included participants aged 15 to 26. The result showed that the program had a positive influence on various aspects, including self-improvement, physical well-being, humility, obedience, and maturity. Another study by Muhallin (2021) investigated the effects of NSTP programs at the University of Cagayan Valley, specifically focusing on the ROTC program. The research revealed that the ROTC program had a positive influence on students' development, particularly in promoting ethics, patriotism, voluntarism, and national defense. The ROTC program scored 3.38, indicating its significant impact on students' self-development. Likewise, Atillano et al. (2022) examined the impact of the National Service Training Program (NSTP) on 104 Dominican students. The findings demonstrated the positive influence of NSTP classes. The majority of respondents strongly agreed that the program helped them take responsibility for their behavior in the community, discover their role in society, and inspired them to become effective leaders. The overall influence was considered very high, with a mean of 4.30 and a standard deviation of 0.53.

On the other hand, Campbell (2018) conducted a study to investigate the relationship between military management and the prevalence of medial tibial stress syndrome (MTSS) among ROTC cadets. The study involved a self-reporting survey completed by 63 ROTC cadets, with an average age of 20 years old. The findings indicated that 56.1% of the 58 respondents experienced MTSS since joining the ROTC program. Additionally, Smith et al. (2020) estimated the prevalence of Eating Disorder Risk (EDR) and Body Image Dissatisfaction (BID) among ROTC cadets. The study utilized a Likert-Scale instrument and considered various demographics, such as sex, age, ethnicity, military branch,

and self-reported height and weight. The results indicated that 33 (32.4%) of the respondents were at risk of developing EDRs. The study also found that both male and female cadets had larger figures than their ideal body image. To prevent EDRs and BID, ROTC cadets should balance physical training sessions with their academic workload. Another study conducted by Ha et al. (2020) investigated the mediating effect of the stress response on soldiers' perceived stress and military life adjustment. The Perceived Stress Scale, consisting of five subscales (role and relationship stress, environmental stress, work stress, leisure stress, and outside-of-corps stress) was employed in the study, which involved 300 army soldiers, with 285 completed the survey. The findings revealed that higher levels of perceived stress were associated with difficulties in military life adjustment. Furthermore, group cohesion directly influenced the relationship between perceived stress and military adjustment, with respondents reporting higher group cohesion scores finding it easier to adjust to military life.

F. Synthesis

Over the years, there have been changes in the implementation of the ROTC Program in the Philippines. It was initially established in 1935, but in 2002, Republic Act No. 9163 introduced the National Service Training Program (NSTP), which made ROTC an optional program. However, in 2022, new Senate Bills proposed by the Congress of the Philippines aimed to reintroduce the ROTC Program as a mandatory requirement for undergraduate students. These bills argue that the MBROTC Program would contribute to student's social development and enhance the country's capacity to respond to disasters and national security threats.

Based on the reviewed research and government documents, it has been found that the ROTC program has a positive influence on the social development of students (Atillano et al., 2022; Muhallin, 2021; Pacatang & Montalla, 2021). However, other studies and literature have highlighted negative perceptions of the ROTC program, with historical issues such as bullying and hazing being

identified. Measures like R.A. No. 9163 and the Anti-Hazing Act of 2018 have been implemented to address these concerns. Furthermore, the ROTC program has been shown to pose physical and mental health risks to students (Campbell, 2018; Ha et al., 2020; Smith et al., 2020). Previous studies have revealed alleged cases of corruption and health risks that jeopardize students' well-being (Leal, 2006; Smith et al., 2020; Ha et al., 2020).

While studies have been conducted to investigate students' perceptions of the ROTC program in the Philippines, most of them have focused on students who voluntarily enrolled in the program and are already in college (Piatka, 2022; Tullao, 2019; Muhallin, 2021). Additionally, there is a lack of studies exploring the perceptions of parents of the ROTC program in the Philippines, indicating a knowledge gap.

G. Conceptual Framework

Fig. 1 presents the conceptual framework of the study, which encompasses three main themes related to the Mandatory Basic ROTC program. These themes were identified through a review of relevant literature and Senate Bill No. 236. It focused on the following: (1) social development of students which encompasses the growth of their leadership, social interaction skills, awareness in society, and engagement in community projects, (2) disaster preparedness and national security which encompass the fostering of patriotism, strengthening the country's response to natural calamities, defending against foreign invasions, and countering domestic attacks to safeguard the well-being and stability of the nation of the students, (3) issues regarding the ROTC program refers to concerns encompassing the potential risks to physical and mental well-being, the possibility of abuse of power by ROTC officers, and the vulnerability to incidents of hazing within the program. By examining these three main themes, the study aimed to provide insights into the perceptions of both students and parents regarding the implementation of the MBROTC program in the Philippines.

Fig. 1: Conceptual framework of the study

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

The researchers employed a quantitative research approach. Specifically, this study used a descriptive research design. Descriptive research aims to describe individuals or a population by studying them without manipulating the variables or characteristics needed from a respondent (Siedlecki, 2020). This design was suitable for the study as it allowed for the description of perceptions of the respondents, specifically parents and Grade 11 to 12 students.

B. Context and Participants

The participants of this study were Grade 11 and 12 students, and parents in Metro Manila, Philippines. To ensure the validity of the collected data, the researchers established specific criteria for the respondents. For students, they should be grade 11 or grade 12 students planning to pursue college education in the Philippines for the academic year 2023 – 2024, and currently studying in Metro Manila. For the parents, they should have children currently enrolled in grades 11 or 12 levels, planning to

pursue college education in the Philippines for the academic year 2023 – 2024, and their children were studying in Metro Manila. These characteristics were chosen because the MBROTC Program proposals aim to implement the program in higher-level or college education. Finally, quota sampling was utilized to gather 196 students and 196 parents with a total of 392 respondents.

C. Research Instruments

The researchers employed a Likert-scale questionnaire with the following descriptive scales: 1 – strongly disagree, 2 – disagree, 3 – unsure, 4 – agree, and 5 – strongly agree. In addition, two separate surveys were conducted using Microsoft Forms, one for student-respondents and another for parent-respondents. The questionnaire consisted of three sections. The first section comprised an online consent form for students and parents, followed by a section profiling the respondents. The remaining section included statements aimed at assessing the perception of students regarding the implementation of the Mandatory Basic ROTC program, specifically focusing on (a) the social development of a student, (b) disaster preparedness and national security, and (c) issues related to the ROTC program with each theme contained four statements.

To establish the validity questionnaire, the researchers utilized Lawshe’s content validity index. Three content experts about the ROTC Program were invited to validate the questionnaire. The researchers revised the questionnaire based on the feedback from the validators and achieved a content validity ratio of 1.00 which showed a high content validity of the questionnaire. Following the validation of the questionnaire, pilot testing was conducted on a sample of 15 respondents to identify any potential errors or issues that could affect the validity of the result. Subsequently, Cronbach’s alpha was employed to assess the reliability of the questionnaire. The social development of students, the country’s disaster preparedness and national security, and issues concerning the ROTC program obtained a reliability coefficient between 0.79 to 0.97. This showed that the questionnaire is reliable.

D. Data-gathering Procedure

Initially, the researchers developed a questionnaire based on a comprehensive review of relevant literature. This questionnaire went through validity and reliability testing to increase the validity of the result of this study. Following this, the researchers prepared a letter of permission to conduct a study from different schools in Metro Manila. To ensure that ethical guidelines were followed, researchers created an informed consent form, emphasizing the purpose and procedure of the study, possible risks and discomfort, and confidentiality of the data. The participants were also informed that they have the right to accept or refuse to participate in this study. Once the pre-data gathering phase was concluded, the researchers began collecting data from the selected participants. They utilized Microsoft Forms to distribute the questionnaire. Participants were provided with an online consent form. For student respondents who were not of legal age, a parent's consent form was given. The researchers emphasized that there were no right or wrong answers and encouraged participants to respond honestly and seriously. Upon agreement, the participants proceeded to fill out the survey, which was expected to take approximately five minutes to complete. The researchers used Microsoft Excel to organize the collected data and utilized SPSS software to analyze the data gathered.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Perception of students-respondents on the implementation of the Mandatory Basic ROTC Program in terms of the social development of a student

Table I presents the perceptions of students regarding the implementation of the MBROTC program on their social development. The results indicate that a significant proportion, specifically 118 students, accounting for 59% of the total student-respondents, expressed agreement or strong agreement that the implementation of the MBROTC Program would effectively teach them to participate in community projects. Likewise, more than half of student-respondents tend to agree or strongly agree that MBROTC will develop their leadership skills, social interaction skills, and will help them realize their role in society. These findings provide substantial validation for the objectives outlined in S.B No. 236 and S.B No. 1551, which emphasize the importance of the MBROTC program in fostering students' social development and cultivating leadership qualities within the community.

Table 1: Summary of response from Student-respondents in terms of Social Development of a Student

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
Develop my leadership skills in the community.	22 11.2%	23 11.7%	48 24.4%	52 26.4%	52 26.4%
Enhance my social interaction skills in the community.	20 10.2%	22 11.2%	52 21.3%	62 31.5%	51 25.9%
Help me realize my role in society.	27 13.7%	24 12.2%	41 20.8%	59 29.9%	46 23.4%
Teach me to participate in community projects.	24 12.2%	24 12.2%	31 15.7%	66 33.5%	52 26.4%

Legends: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, U – Unsure, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree

B. Perception of students-respondents on the implementation of the Mandatory Basic ROTC Program in terms of the country's disaster preparedness and national Security.

Table II represents the perception of students on the implementation of the MBROTC Program in terms of disaster preparedness and national security. The results show that more than half of the students-respondents tend to agree or strongly agree that the MBROTC program will develop the country's capability to respond to natural calamities, enhance the country's capacity to counter external forces and improve the country's capability to counter domestic attacks. However, the result also shows that 73 or 37% of respondents are unsure of the MBROTC

Program instilling patriotism in them, which in comparison, go against the objective of S.B No. 236 and 1551, which is that the MBROTC Program is to inculcate patriotism in a student. A possible implication for this outcome could be that compared to the reviewed literature, wherein a majority of cited literature was conducted on students who willingly enrolled in the ROTC Program, proposals for the intended implementation of the ROTC Program aim to make the program mandated, which means that incoming college students for the A.Y 2023-2024 or beyond would be required to undergo the MBROTC Program for 2 years, compared to being given a choice during prior academic years.

Table 2: Summary of response from student-respondents in terms of country's disaster preparedness and national security

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
Instill patriotism in me.	21 10.7%	31 15.7%	73 37.1%	47 23.9%	25 12.7%
Develop the country's ability to respond to natural calamities (earthquakes, typhoons, volcanic eruptions).	21 10.7%	17 8.6%	33 16.8%	67 34.0%	59 29.9%
Enhance the country's capacity to defend itself against foreign invasions.	22 11.2%	16 8.1%	40 20.3%	69 35.0%	50 25.4%
Improve the country's capability to counter domestic attacks.	20 10.2%	19 9.6%	42 21.3%	64 32.5%	52 26.4%

Legends: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, U – Unsure, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree

C. Perception of students-respondents on the implementation of the Mandatory Basic ROTC Program in terms of issues regarding the ROTC Program

Table III represents students' perceptions on the implementation of the MBROTC Program in terms of issues regarding the ROTC Program. The data reveals that a significant number of students are unsure if the implementation of the MBROTC will feature issues threatening their well-being or exposing them to corrupt ROTC officers. Specifically, 57 or approximately 29% of the respondents are unsure if the MBROTC Program would threaten their mental well-being while conversely, only a combined 61 or 31% of respondents express agreement or strong agreement that the MBROTC Program will not put them at risk of officers abusing their power. A possible

reason for this could be because of previous cases of hazing which have caused controversy that led to the enactment of R.A No, 9163, which implemented the NSTP Program, allowing students to choose other programs besides the ROTC Program. Other possibilities could be found in Ha et al. (2020) study. They stated that if a student or cadet's stress levels are high, military life adjustment could be difficult which may risk their mental well-being. Since the ROTC Program plans to be mandated, incoming college students may experience military-life adjustment to be able to handle the MBROTC Program. Since they are also managing academics, this may affect their overall well-being by having to undergo military-level training while managing academic performance.

Table 3: Summary of response from student-respondents in terms of issues regarding the rotc program

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
Risk my physical well-being.	38 19.3%	45 22.8%	52 26.4%	41 20.8%	21 10.7%
Threaten my mental well-being.	35 17.8%	45 22.8%	57 28.9%	36 18.3%	24 12.2%
Put me at risk of ROTC Officers abusing their power.	44 22.3%	41 20.8%	51 25.9%	38 19.3%	23 11.7%
Make me vulnerable to possible hazing.	41 20.8%	44 22.3%	44 22.3%	40 20.3%	28 14.2%

Legends: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, U – Unsure, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree

D. Perception of parent-respondents on the implementation of the Mandatory Basic ROTC Program in terms of the social development of a student

Table IV represents the perception of parents on the implementation of the MBROTC program in terms of a student’s social development. The findings reveal that a significant number of parents express agreement or strong agreement that the implementation of MBROTC Program would believe that the implementation of the MBROTC program would socially develop a student, with 149 or approximately 76% of respondents expressing agreement-strong agreement that the MBROTC Program teaches students to participate in community projects while only a

combined 23 parents express disagreement or strong disagreement that the MBROTC program would enhance a student’s social interaction skills in the community. This implies that parents express a positive perception toward the MBROTC Program in terms of the social development of a student. As stated earlier, these findings validate the objectives of S.B no. 236 and S.B no. 1551, which state that the MBROTC Program would help develop a student’s social development. These results also validate the findings of Muhallin (2021) and Tullao (2019), whose studies found that the NSTP and ROTC Programs helped instill the concept of leadership within the community among students.

Table 4: Summary of response from parent-respondents in terms of social development of a student

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
Develop a student’s leadership skills in the community.	8 4.1%	18 9.2%	16 8.2%	56 28.6%	98 50.0%
Enhance a student’s social interaction in the community.	10 5.1%	17 8.7%	20 10.2%	50 25.5%	99 50.5%
Help a student realize their role in society.	8 4.1%	15 7.7%	17 8.7%	62 31.6%	94 48.0%
Teach a student to participate in community projects.	9 4.6%	14 7.1%	17 8.7%	61 31.1%	95 48.5%

Legends: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, U – Unsure, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree

E. Perception parent-respondents on the implementation of the Mandatory Basic ROTC Program in terms of the country’s disaster preparedness and national security

Table V reveals the results of a parent’s perception of the implementation of the MBROTC in terms of the country’s disaster preparedness and national security. The results show that 158 or 81% of parents agree or strongly agree that the implementation of the MBROTC Program would enhance the country’s capability to respond to domestic attacks while the majority of parents also agree that implementation of the MBROTC Program would instill patriotism in a student, enhance the country’s capacity to defend itself from foreign invaders and improve the country’s capability to respond to domestic forces. Conversely, only 20 parents express disagreement that the MBROTC Program would improve the country’s

capability to defend itself from foreign invasions and domestic attacks respectively. This implies that parents have positive perceptions toward the implementation of the MBROTC Program in terms of the country’s disaster preparedness and national security, providing substantial validation for the objective of the MBROTC Program when it comes to preparing the country and its citizens in the event of a national threat or disaster. A possible explanation for this outcome could be due to the benefits of preparing students in the event of a natural disaster or attack. If the MBROTC Program were to be implemented, students would be prepared to respond to events that may put the lives of the population at risk such as natural disasters and foreign attacks. The MBROTC Program would help the country quickly defend itself or respond to quickly recover from the effects of war or disaster.

Table 5: Summary of response from parent-respondents in terms of country’s disaster preparedness and national security

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
Instill patriotism in a student.	9 (4.6%)	15 (7.7%)	31 (15.8%)	62 (31.6%)	79 (40.3%)
Develop the country’s ability to respond to natural calamities (earthquakes, typhoons, volcanic eruptions).	9 4.6%	14 7.1%	23 11.7%	49 25.0%	101 51.5%
Enhance the country’s capacity to defend itself against foreign invasions.	10 5.1%	10 5.1%	18 9.2%	62 31.6%	96 49.0%
Improve the country’s capability to counter domestic attacks.	10 5.1%	10 5.1%	18 9.2%	56 28.6%	102 52.0%

Legends: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, U – Unsure, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree

F. Perception of parent respondents on the implementation of the Mandatory Basic ROTC Program in terms of issues regarding the ROTC Program

Table VI reveals findings regarding the perception of parents on issues within the ROTC Program. The data shows that parents tend to agree that the MBROTC Program would not risk a student’s physical well-being and would not put them at risk of hazing and officers abusing their power. However, the data also reveals that 54 or approximately 28% of respondents are unsure if the MBROTC Program

would risk the mental well-being of a student. As mentioned earlier, a reason for this could be the adjustment that incoming college students would have to undergo to manage military-level training and academic responsibilities. According to Ha et al. (2020), higher levels of stress impact a student’s capability to adjust to military training. This could be a possible explanation as to why parents are still skeptical or unsure of the effects of the MBROTC Program on a student’s mental well-being.

Table 6: Summary of parent-respondents in terms of issues regarding the ROTC program

Statement	SD	D	U	A	SA
Risk a student’s physical well-being.	20 10.2%	28 14.3%	41 20.9%	71 36.2%	36 18.4%
Threaten a student’s mental well-being.	19 9.7%	30 15.3%	54 27.6%	58 29.6%	35 17.9%
Put a student at risk of ROTC Officers abusing their power.	18 9.2%	39 19.9%	36 18.4%	65 33.2%	38 19.4%
Make a student vulnerable to possible hazing.	27 13.8%	32 16.3%	38 19.4%	59 30.1%	40 20.4%

Legends: SD – Strongly Disagree, D – Disagree, U – Unsure, A – Agree, SA – Strongly Agree

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter summarizes the study's findings, draws implications from the findings, and offers recommendations from the researchers based on the findings and limitations.

A. Summary of the Findings

From the analysis of data and results obtained, the findings were summarized in the following:

- Both students and parents tend to agree or strongly agree that the implementation of the MBROTC Program would be effective in the student’s social development.
- Students and parents tend to agree that the implementation of the MBROTC Program would develop the country’s capability to respond to disasters as well as enhance the country’s national security. However, students are still unsure of the effectiveness of the MBROTC Program to instill patriotism in a student.
- The findings reveal that students are still unsure if the MBROTC program will be a risk to their overall well-being or expose them to abuse from the officers or hazing among cadets. Conversely, parents tend to agree that the implementation of the MBROTC program will not risk the student’s physical well-being or expose them to corrupt officers. However, they are still unsure if the MBROTC program would threaten a student’s mental well-being.

B. Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings:

- Students positively perceive that the implementation of the MBROTC Program will aid their social development while parents are slightly more positive on their perception about it.
- The parents are slightly more positive than the students that the implementation of the MBROTC would help in the country’s disaster preparedness and national security.

However, students were not sure whether it will instill patriotism in them.

- Parents positively believe that the implementation of the MBROTC program will not expose their children to physical and mental risk, corrupt ROTC officers, and possible hazing experiences. However, students are skeptical about the said issues.

C. Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the above conclusions:

- To address the uncertainty of students regarding the MBROTC Program's impact on patriotism, it is recommended to revisit the current ROTC program implemented in higher education to explain why the students are skeptical that MBROTC will instill patriotism in them.
- To address the disparity in beliefs between parents and students regarding physical and mental risks, corrupt officers, and hazing experiences, the legislators must establish clear protocols and mechanisms for student safety. Implementing training programs for ROTC officers, regular evaluations, and reporting systems can ensure the physical and mental well-being of students. Providing platforms for student input and involving them in the development of anti-hazing policies can also address their skepticism and promote a positive and inclusive environment within the program.
- Future researchers should consider conducting qualitative studies to delve deeper into the underlying factors contributing to the differences in perception between parents and students. In-depth interviews and focus groups can provide valuable insights into the specific concerns, motivations, and expectations of both groups. Additionally, exploring the long-term effects of the MBROTC Program on participants' social development, disaster preparedness, national security awareness, and

patriotism can provide a comprehensive understanding of its overall impact. Such research can guide program improvements and inform effective strategies for engaging both parents and students in the future.

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